

On-site activity determination of ^{211}At using absolute 4pi-alpha liquid scintillation counting and HPGe

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ABSTRACT

For accurate activity measurements and to comply with EU regulations traceability is required. For alpha emitters of interest for emerging targeted alpha therapies (TAT), like ^{211}At , standardised samples are not readily available. The use of gamma spectrometry can come with high uncertainties due to its reliance on decay data for gamma emissions. A new method for determining the activity of ^{211}At in a clinical setting is proposed, i.e. on-site measurement, using absolute 4pi-alpha liquid scintillation counting (LSC) with thresholding on a portable TDCR counter. The method focuses on measuring only the alpha particles and not the electrons, which emission intensities come with a higher uncertainty. Using the absolute LSC method the relative expanded measurement uncertainty was 2.2 % ($k = 2$). A comparison using gamma spectrometry and the more readily available high purity germanium (HPGe) detector, the relative expanded uncertainty was 12 % ($k = 2$). The largest contribution to the much higher uncertainty of the gamma spectrometry comes from the uncertainties in the decay data. Using a portable TDCR-detector is a viable approach to establishing traceability for ^{211}At , where transportation to a national metrology lab is not feasible. With better decay data the uncertainty of the gamma spectrometry can be reduced by at least one third, which would make it a better alternative when absolute measurements are not available.

1 Introduction

Targeted alpha therapy (TAT) is an expanding field within cancer treatments with a growing number of radiopharmaceuticals in clinical trials (Jang et al., 2023). One of the alpha-emitters being investigated is ^{211}At (Albertsson et al., 2023). At Sahlgrenska University Hospital (Gothenburg, Sweden), a clinical phase I study with ^{211}At has been completed (Andersson et al., 2009; Hallqvist et al., 2019), and additional trials are planned. In order to optimise the treatments and to fulfil the requirements of patient specific dosimetry (Euratom, 2013), accurate activity measurements are necessary. Currently, there is no established method for traceable activity measurements for ^{211}At in a clinical setting. The most accessible way would be to use a high purity germanium (HPGe) detector, but its calibration would involve fitting with gamma peaks from other nuclides. It is also reliant on accurate decay

data particularly of the photon emissions. The Decay Data Evaluation Project (DDEP) bases its evaluations on measurements, which for ^{211}At are generally lacking. Therefore, HPGe detector measurements of ^{211}At come with relatively high uncertainties.

Another option would be to use liquid scintillation counting and the triple-to-double coincidence ratio (TDCR) method (Broda et al., 2007). Liquid scintillation counting using the free parameter model is an excellent tool to determine the activity of radionuclides with complex decay schemes like ^{222}Rn (Cassette et al., 2006), ^{223}Ra (Cessna and Zimmerman, 2010), ^{227}Ac (Kossert et al., 2015) or ^{229}Th (Kossert et al., 2014) in equilibrium with their progenies. Some of the corresponding decay chains are comprised of very short-lived progenies, and their decays may therefore occur during the dead-time of the detector. To compensate for this, a detector with variable dead-time is required. Then an effective dead-time can be determined which allows extrapolation to

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zero dead-time counting rates (Cassette et al., 2006) or an adapted model that use the dead time value as demonstrated by (Bergeron et al., 2022). This is not the objective of the work presented in this paper as we want to avoid the use of complex models and propose a simpler solution for on-site activity measurements.

While it is possible to measure both betas and alphas, it is more challenging to perform measurements where both are present. ^{211}At decays either by alpha emission to ^{207}Bi or through electron capture (EC) to ^{211}Po as described in Fig. 1. The data for the Auger electrons resulting from the EC decay is based on modelling using BetaShape (Mougeot, 2019, 2023). This is a complex process for high-Z nuclides as EC and β^+ transitions are in competition, which leads to higher uncertainties. Therefore, the aim was to only measure the alphas from the ^{211}At decay and the uncertainty.

The solid targets used in this work were irradiated in Copenhagen, Denmark and then transported to Gothenburg, Sweden for separation of the astatine from the target materials. Since Sweden does not have a national metrology laboratory for radioactivity measurements, the relatively short half-life ($t_{1/2} = 7.216$ (7) h) of ^{211}At necessitates absolute measurements to be performed on-site. An additional challenge is that coproduced ^{210}At cannot be separated from ^{211}At . The varying amount of this impurity is depending on the energy of the He^+ in the cyclotron (Henriksen et al., 2001; Lambrecht and Mirzadeh, 1985; Sevenois et al., 2024).

Using, to our knowledge for the first time, absolute 4pi-alpha liquid scintillation counting with thresholding on a portable TDCR counter to measure ^{211}At in a clinical setting helped us overcome these challenges. Using a portable micro-TDCR, our aim was to establish a method that allowed the calibration of measurement devices within the hospital department to be made with metrological traceability.

2. Methods

2.1. Preparation of ^{211}At stock solution

^{211}At was produced at the Copenhagen University Hospital, Copenhagen, Denmark, using their Scanditronic MC32-NI cyclotron. A ^{209}Bi

target was bombarded with He^+ of about 29.5 MeV (Lindgren). The target was transported to the radiopharmacy laboratory at Sahlgrenska University Hospital, Gothenburg, Sweden (Sahlgrenska). There it was dry distilled, using an automated module (Atley C100, Atley Solutions AB), and the astatine eluted in CHCl_3 , which was then evaporated to dryness using N_2 (Aneheim et al., 2015). Approximately 125 MBq of the dried ^{211}At was dissolved in 55 mL 0.2M NaOH and 20 mM NaI and homogenised using a vortex. All further dilutions were made using the 0.2M NaOH and 20 mM NaI solution unless otherwise stated. From the dissolved ^{211}At , approximately 1 MBq was taken and diluted to a total volume of 7 mL to form a stock solution. Weight was always used to calculate dilution factors (Fig. 2). A Sartorius ME 5 precision balance was used for the liquid scintillation samples and for all other samples a Sartorius MC210P balance was used.

All activity measurements were decay corrected to the reference time (T_{ref}) 12:00 CET on the first day of measurements (day one) and all decay data were taken from (DDEP, 2024) unless stated otherwise. All equipment used is regularly monitored for quality assurance and validated for clinical applications.

2.2. Absolute 4pi-alpha liquid scintillation counting

Since one single alpha decay generates many scintillation photons, a detection efficiency of 1 was assumed. The number of alpha particles per decay is well established and is presented with a low uncertainty (DDEP, 2024). The threshold of each of the three photomultiplier tubes (PMT) was adjusted in the combined real-time TDCR counting system and multichannel analyser, labZY nanoTDCR (Model TD9010, YANTEL LLC), using the labZY-TDCR software (LabZY TDCR 10.7, YANTEL LLC). Both were developed for on-site TDCR measurement (Jordanov et al., 2020) so that only the signal from the alphas was detected. The method was previously validated using ^{241}Am (Sabot et al., 2022). Two indicators were used to optimise the threshold settings. One was the triple-to-double coincidence ratio, which should be close to one when detecting only alphas. The other indication was a variation in the double coincidence rate (D) around the set thresholds. If the threshold is set too low, both alphas and electrons are detected, and the count rate increases. If the threshold is set too high not all alphas are detected resulting in a decreased count rate.

On day one, all liquid scintillation samples were prepared from the stock solution. Two types of samples were prepared using either 20 mL scintillation vials made of glass (borosilicate, Duran Wheaton Kimble) or plastic ("Anti-Static Super Polyethylene", Revvity).

- 20 mL glass vials with 15 mL of liquid scintillator Ultima Gold AB®, 1 mL of water (MilliQ-water 18.2 M Ω *cm), and 105–174 mg of stock solution (6 samples)
- 20 mL plastic vials with 10 mL of Ultima Gold AB® and 101–135 mg of stock solution (5 samples).

The stock solution was added to the cocktail using a micro-pycnometer and the mixture was then thoroughly shaken to ensure homogeneity. Blank control samples were prepared for each type of vial. Once thresholds were set, the activity of the LSC samples were measured and calculated assuming a detection efficiency of 1 using the counting rate D. All corrections were thereafter applied.

2.3. Gamma spectrometry

A small amount of the alpha-emitter ^{210}At is typically co-produced with ^{211}At and the portable TDCR counter cannot discriminate between alpha particles originating from different nuclides. Therefore, gamma spectrometry was used to estimate the fraction of alpha-emitting impurities. Two samples from the stock solution were measured for 20 h using a coaxial HPGe detector (Model GC1018, Mirion (Canberra)) and analysed using Mirion's Apex-Gamma™ software. Since data for ^{210}At is

Fig. 1. Decay scheme of ^{211}At . Decay data from (DDEP, 2024).

Fig. 2. Illustration of sample preparation for the absolute 4pi-alpha LSC and gamma spectrometry (HPGe).

not available from DDEP, it was taken from ENSDF (IAEA, 2024).

The reference geometry used for gamma spectrometry was 1.5 mL of solution in a glass vial (SureSTART™ GC Vial <2 mL, Thermo Scientific) calibrated using a multi gamma cocktail (12ML01, LEA). The first sample consisted of 1.5 mL stock solution and the second sample was prepared using 1.0 mL of stock solution and diluted to a total volume of 1.5 mL.

3. Results

3.1. Absolute 4pi-alpha liquid scintillation counting

To validate that we only measured the alpha particles with the TDCR

counter a spectrum was plotted (Fig. 3) in measuring one sample. From the plot, the difference in energy between electron capture and alpha decay is apparent. The large composite peak is the result of the different energies of the alpha emissions from ^{211}At and its daughter ^{211}Po . The broadening is compounded by the relatively low resolution of the TDCR counter due to the highly reflective and scattering surface of the optical chamber.

The optimal threshold for the PMTs to only detect alphas was found to be -230 mV on each PMT, which resulted from a Triple-to-Double coincidence ratio (T/D) of 0.9988 (4) (Fig. 4). The obtained T/D was thus not exactly one. Also, the double coincidence ratio was found to be stable at this threshold, which can be seen in Fig. 5. The measurement uncertainty associated with this method is estimated to 0.2 %, including

Fig. 3. Spectrum obtained from one PMT from the TDCR counter with ^{211}At solution using Ultima Gold AB. The large composite peak is the result of the different energies of the alpha emissions from ^{211}At and its daughter ^{211}Po combined with the poor resolution of the device due to high reflective and scattering surface inside the optical chamber. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 4. Variation of Triple-to-Double (T/D) coincidence ratio as a function of PMT threshold with ^{211}At solution using Ultima Gold AB. The uncertainties correspond to the standard deviation of 10 consecutive measurements. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 5. The double coincidence count rate (D) and triple coincidence count rate (T) as a function of PMT threshold with ^{211}At solution using Ultima Gold AB. The uncertainties correspond to the standard deviation of 10 consecutive measurements. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

the expected efficiency loss and the statistical fluctuation of the results.

With this threshold setting, the activity of each sample was calculated based only on the alpha emissions. The detection efficiency for alpha particles was assumed to be one. The uncertainties associated with the calculated activities are presented in Table 1. The instrumentation characteristics of the portable TDCR-system are identical to those at LNHB (Sabot et al., 2022), possibly featuring even lower intrinsic motion. Two sets of background measurements for double coincidences (D) were performed, each set consisted of 11 consecutive measurements and its uncertainty based on the standard deviation (dead time 50 μs and coincidence window of 40 ns). The long measurements lasted for 1h and the short for 100s, which is identical to the measurement time of the

actual samples. The background count rate D for the long measurements was 2.60 (6) s^{-1} and for the short D = 2.57 (19) s^{-1} . The background was clearly negligible compared to the D counting rate of the samples that were between 50 000 s^{-1} down to 7000 s^{-1} . Corrections for accidental coincidences (Dutsov et al., 2020) and asymmetry (Kossert et al., 2020a) were applied and both found to be <0.01 % (Table 1).

The first series of measurements was conducted on six samples prepared using 10 mL of Ultima Gold AB and 1 mL of water (MilliQ-water 18.2 $\text{M}\Omega\cdot\text{cm}$) in glass vials. The activities were calculated based on the counting rate D, considering the probabilities of alpha emissions throughout the entire ^{211}At decay chain (^{211}At and ^{211}Po) at secular equilibrium. For the decay of one atom of ^{211}At , exactly one alpha

Table 1

Uncertainty budget for one measurement with the portable TDCR counter sample with a plastic vial and UG AB.

Component	Relative standard measurement uncertainty (%)
Background	0.02 %
Counting rate	0.1 %
Deadtime, counter linearity	0.01 %
Impurities	0.01 %
Emission intensity	0.2 %
Model (Threshold technique)	0.2 %
Asymmetry	<0.01 %
Decay correction to reference time	0.2 %
Decay correction during measurement	<0.01 %
Accidental Coincidence	<0.01 %
Mass	0.2 %
Combined relative standard uncertainty	0.4 %

particle is expected and at secular equilibrium 1.0000 (14) alphas are expected using the tool for serial decay on (LARAWEB, 2024). As shown in Fig. 6, the results obtained for the samples deviated with an apparent correlation to their sample number and thus the time at which they were prepared.

Repeated measurements were conducted on the first sample at different time intervals (Fig. 7). The coefficient of variation (CV) of the repeated measurement was 0.28 %, which is lower than what was observed for the total set of samples (0.76 %).

Activity measurements on the series of samples based on Ultima Gold AB in plastic vials also exhibit a notable inconsistency with a CV of 0.93 % (Fig. 8). It differs from the series using glass vials (Fig. 6) in that there is no apparent correlation with the time with which they were prepared.

Again, repeated measurements were conducted on sample 7 at different time intervals (Fig. 9). Between each measurement the vial was removed from the device and then placed back. The potential change in geometry is represented in the measurement uncertainty. The CV of the repeated measurement was 0.06 %, which was considered acceptable. From this, plastic vials with Ultima Gold AB seems to provide the best stability in our case.

3.2. Gamma spectrometry

The resulting spectrum from using the HPGe detector is presented in Fig. 10. The main gamma peaks of ^{211}At , its daughters ^{207}Bi and ^{211}Po , as well as the presence of the impurity ^{210}At were identified. The detector efficiency curve was established with a multi-gamma source in the same geometry. For sample HPGe-1, the activity concentration (at the reference time) of ^{210}At was measured at 23.3 (14) $\text{Bq}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$, compared to 130.9 (79) $\text{kBq}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ ^{211}At . This corresponds to an impurity ratio of 0.01 % of ^{210}At in the ^{211}At solution.

Using the calibration curve, an uncertainty budget was derived for the HPGe measurement (Table 2). The uncertainty induced by the source position, dimensions, and medium transfer was calculated using ETNA (Radu et al., 2009) and the 1 % estimator for the peak at 687.2 keV, with a distance of 44.4 (5) mm between the bottom of the source and the detector window, a sample diameter of 12.0 (5) mm, and a fill height of 21.5 (5) mm. The coincidence correction factor is calculated by ETNA (Lépy et al., 2015) as 1.001758 for the same peak; therefore, to remain conservative, the uncertainty due to coincidences is set to 0.17 %. The emission intensity is taken from DDEP and results in a 4.8 % uncertainty, the second largest factor is the calibration curve of the HPGe (3.4 %) while the other parameters are negligible resulting in a combined relative standard uncertainty of 6.2 %.

For HPGe sample measured 8.6h after the reference time, the activity concentration was determined to be 129.4 (78) $\text{kBq}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ for ^{211}At at the reference time, a deviation of <1 % compared to the first HPGe sample.

4. Discussion

This work includes results from using both glass and plastic vials for determining ^{211}At activity. There was a variation in measured activity concentration between the samples in the first batch using glass vials with a CV of 0.76 % as can be seen in Fig. 6, and for the second batch using plastic vials a CV of 0.93 % as can be seen in Fig. 8. The average activity concentration is also 1.2 % higher in the first batch compared to the second. The reason for the variation within and between the batches is unclear, but most likely it was due to the source preparation as the variation cannot be explained by the measurement uncertainty. One hypothesis is that adsorption on the walls of the transfer pipette used for the LS sample preparations lead to a decrease in activity concentration of the sample, even though precautions were taken to avoid this

Fig. 6. Variation in activity between samples relative to the average for stock solution in 15 mL of Ultima Gold AB and 1 mL H_2O in glass vial. The uncertainties correspond to the standard uncertainties as evaluated in Table 1. Decay corrected to reference time. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 7. Repeated measurements of sample 1 with ^{211}At solution inside 15 mL of Ultima Gold AB and 1 mL H_2O in a glass vial relative to the average. The uncertainties correspond to the standard uncertainties as evaluated in Table 1. Decay corrected to reference time. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 8. Measurement of prepared sample of ^{211}At solution inside 10 mL of Ultima Gold AB in plastic vials relative to the average. The uncertainties correspond to the standard uncertainties as evaluated in Table 1. Decay corrected to reference time. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

phenomenon by saturating the pipette with a solution of 0.2M NaOH and 20 mM NaI and letting it dry before use. The pipette was refilled between sample 1 and 2, and between sample 8 and 9. No obvious effect is seen from refilling the pipette between sample 1 and 2, but the refill between sample 8 and 9 correlates with change in activity (Fig. 8). The volume was low and thus the surface-to-volume ratio was high, making it more susceptible to adsorption. The variation was large enough to be detectable with the TDCR counter, but not for the other available detectors in the radiopharmacy lab, given the uncertainties of those detectors. Further measurements with the portable TDCR counter, preferably in comparison with an alternative method of dispensing the samples would most likely resolve this issue.

Adding an aqueous solution to the scintillation cocktail (Kossert et al., 2020b) can increase stability by saturating the hygroscopic

properties of the scintillation cocktails. We used (MilliQ-water 18.2 $\text{M}\Omega\cdot\text{cm}$) as we did not want to raise the pH and risk changing the properties of the scintillation cocktail. This was done to evaluate if it was needed, but the stability of the cocktail was good for both batches, which can be seen in Fig. 7 and Fig. 9.

The inherent asymmetry of the PMTs could not be completely compensated for by individually adjusting the threshold of the PMTs. The impact on the uncertainty was, however, negligible with an estimated standard uncertainty of $<0.01\%$.

Depending on the energy of the He^+ during production varying degrees of ^{210}At could be produced and cannot be separated from ^{211}At . As the ratio in our case was 0.01 % the impact is negligible. This held true for the ingrowth of the ^{211}At 's daughter ^{207}Bi as well because of its long half-life of 32.9 (19) years (DDEP).

Fig. 9. Repeated measurement of sample 7 with ^{211}At solution in 10 mL of Ultima Gold AB in a plastic vial relative to the average. The uncertainties correspond to the standard uncertainties as evaluated in Table 1. Decay corrected to reference time. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 10. Spectrum obtained with the HPGe detector and the ^{211}At stock solution.

The T/D coincidence ratio was almost 1 (Fig. 4) and the discrepancy from being exactly 1 was considered a measurement uncertainty in our method. The source of this uncertainty could not be precisely identified but is potentially linked to the probability of interactions with gammas emitted with the decay of ^{211}At and its daughters.

In the gamma spectrometry measurements, it is worth noting is that the activity concentration varied $<1\%$ between the two samples. They were measured 8.6 h apart and with different initial sample volumes, indicating that any instability and inhomogeneity were within the uncertainty. Gamma spectrometry was performed using all the developed techniques, applying geometry corrections, calibration curves, and

coincidence corrections. It is evident that the dominant contribution to the uncertainty budget is the decay data. Therefore, the measurements presented herein could potentially be used to improve the evaluation of gamma emission intensities. However, due to the added uncertainty from the LSC sample preparation this was not pursued. However, the added uncertainty is relatively low compared to the typical measurement uncertainties of radionuclide calibrators and gamma counters and given the limited options for metrological traceability of At-211 it is still a viable option.

Table 2

Uncertainty budget for HPGe measurement at Sahlgrenska University Hospital using the peak at 687.2 keV for activity calculation.

Component	Relative standard uncertainty (%)
Background	<0.01 %
Counting rate	1.2 %
Efficiency from calibration	3.4 %
Emission intensity	4.8 %
Decay correction to reference time	0.22 %
Decay correction during measurement	<0.01 %
Coincidence correction	0.17 %
Dead time	0.10 %
Geometry transfer and sample dimensions	1.0 %
Mass	0.15 %
Combined relative standard uncertainty	6.2 %

5. Conclusion

An absolute method of determining the activity concentration of $a^{211}\text{At}$ solution using 4pi-alpha LSC with thresholding on a TDCR counter was tested for the first time, on-site, in a clinical setting. The combined standard uncertainty of the measurement was 0.4 %, but there was a CV of 1.0 % between the samples. Taking that into account resulted in a combined standard uncertainty of 1.1 %.

The source of the variation cannot be explained by the uncertainty of the measurement itself and was most likely due to the method of dispensing the stock solution to the samples. The total expanded measurement uncertainty ($k = 2$) of the LS counting, considering the variation in source preparation was 2.2 % resulting in a final activity concentration of $122.0 \pm 2.7 \text{ kBq}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ compared to the plastic vials $121.2 \pm 1.4 \text{ kBq}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ and $122.7 \pm 1.1 \text{ kBq}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ for the glass vials. The same measurement at a national metrology lab would typically encompass a combined standard uncertainty of few per mille. In conclusion, using a portable TDCR counter is a very viable option for determining the activity of ^{211}At , where transportation to a national metrology lab may not be practical, especially if a better method could be developed to avoid the source preparation issues. As demonstrated in this work, gamma spectrometry can be effectively applied in hospitals, making it a promising solution for simultaneously measuring activity concentration and checking for impurities—both of which are critical for preparing clinical batches of radiopharmaceuticals.

Aim

To develop a method to determine the activity concentration of $a^{211}\text{At}$ solution using absolute 4pi-alpha liquid scintillation counting with thresholding on a portable TDCR counter. The method needs to be capable to exclude electron capture (EC) and only measure alpha particles and be useable on-site in a clinical setting.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Leidermark E: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Aneheim E:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Bäck T:** Writing – review & editing. **Lindegren S:** Writing – review & editing. **Jensen H:** Writing – review & editing, Resources. **Dulieu C:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Mougeot X:** Data curation. **Persson L:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Sabot B:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Palm S:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Emma Aneheim reports a relationship with Atley Solutions AB that includes: board membership and equity or stocks. Sture Lindegren reports a relationship with Atley Solutions AB that includes: equity or stocks. Stig Palm reports a relationship with Aprit AB that includes: equity or stocks. Sture Lindegren reports a relationship with Aprit AB that includes: equity or stocks. Emma Aneheim reports a relationship with Aprit AB that includes: equity or stocks. Tom Back reports a relationship with Aprit AB that includes: equity or stocks. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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